

Boer Goat Production Performance, Constraints and Opportunities in Nepal

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Abstract : *Khari goat is an indigenous breed of goat (Capra hircus) in Nepal. Innovative farmers are eager to change the livelihood through raising new and improved breed of goat. This study was conducted to find out the Boer goat production performance, constraints and opportunities in Nepal. Primary data were collected from purposive sample of 43 respondents from Dhading district and 36 Boer and 36 Khari goats from Goat Research Station, Bandipur. The data were analyzed through descriptive statistics and compound growth model. Data revealed that higher number of male in the family with more land holding and high level of awareness and access to training adopted Boer goats. Result drawn through comparison of compound growth rate of goat population and meat production showed increment in goat population by 36% whereas meat production by 35%. In this scenario, scale up of Boer goat in the hills of Nepal will be worthy for both meat production and easy marketing.*

Key words: Boer goat, Khari goat, adoption, compound growth rate

Introduction

Goat (*Capra hircus*) is one of the small ruminants which have been closely associated with the human livelihood. Innovative farmers are realizing that employment generation, livelihood enhancement, nutritional security and availability of food can be increased by raising improved breed of livestock. Most goat breeds in Nepal might have similar lineages especially in the areas having similar ecological zones but newly introduced breed Boer goat have potentiality to sustain in different climatic zone also. Exact origin of Boer goats is not clear, it is believed to be the result of a genetic pooling of African indigenous goats, Indians goats, Angora goats, and with some influence of European dairy goats. It resembles Nubian goats but with a much larger frame size (Christopher D. Lu, 2002).

The goat is characterized with the red headed large framed goat with a white body. It bears short and smooth hair. It is famous for non - seasonal breeder and multiple abilities. Triplets and quadruplets are

fairly common in this breed. These types of goats are famous for the best goat meat of the world and well adapted to both extensive and intensive management systems. Good carcass characteristics that is 25kg for male and 22kg within 100 days after birth. The registered average weight was 120kg and 80kg for buck and doe respectively (Boer goat at Gottingen, 2015).

Giving attention to its potentialities and information, commercial goat farming is an emerging agricultural enterprise in the periphery of road access areas of Nepal. In recent day's milk and meat production through improved breed of goat is one of the incomes generating activity. Improved goat breed farming is becoming popular in Nepal these days. At present, there are more than 10 millions goats in Nepal. Khari goat, which is a local breed, is supposed to be the best goat for Nepalese conditions (CBS, 2015). The average flock size of goat has increased to 1-3 to 4-5 heads and establishment of commercial farm owning 200 to 500 goats is taking at the momentum and the paradigm of the effort of subsistence level have been converted to commercial phase of goat production (Rajwar, 2013). It is reported that the Khari goat can reach up to 25kg only after one year of its birth where as Boer goat gets the same weight when it is around four months. Looking the characteristics features of the Boer goat, keeping the man and technology constant people can get higher profit from the goat farming if Boer goat production technology is introduced in Nepal. This effort has led the government of Nepal with its respective department, regional directorates and district offices to launch various programs for the income generation of the poor farmers of Nepal. So, policymakers, researchers and development authorities were humbly requested to think and execute the goat production technology (Nepalese Society of Goettingen, 2015). After several studies and reviewing issues and the research validation have been executed by ARS, Bandipur but still issue of variability in performance, constraints and potentialities are lacking to address. Therefore, the study on Boer goat production performance

opportunities and constraints in Nepal was needed to be undertaken.

Objective

Performance analysis and economic age identification. Assessing constraints and potentiality of scaling up

Methodology

Dharke, Dhading Besi, Chap VDCs of the Dhading district was selected as the site for this study. These sites were selected purposively as the Boer goat producing site as mentioned by DLSO. KII was done with District Livestock Service Office (DLSO) representative of Dhading district. Data regarding the characteristics of farmers, factors influencing technology adoption, farm resources and compatibility with farming system was explored. Household survey was conducted to determine the adoption factor of Boer goat. In addition to this research data from Goat Research Program Bandipur and Out Reach site Gorkha has been

collected to determine the weight varying due to varying in age of Boer goat. Total 36 Boer kids and 36 Khari kids has been measured in Goat Research Project since the birth of the kids.

Result and discussion

Socio-economic characteristics

Data from the variables related to socio-economic characteristics were analyzed to find out the mean difference and also *t* value was calculated. Among the selected variables involvement of male, farm land holding size, access to credit and training variables were highly significant at 1 percent. The contribution of economically active age was significant at 1 percent. Involvement of male farmer in Boer goat production was highly significant at 1 percent level of significance. Land area, access to credit and training taken was also highly significant at 1 percent for the adoption of Boer goat.

Table:1 Mean comparison of socio-demographic characteristic of Survey area

Socio-demographic characteristics	Total (N=75)	Boer goat Adoption		Standard deviation	Mean difference	T value N=43
		Yes n = 15	No n = 28			
Gender	0.40	0.4	0.39	.49	0.01	0.04
Ethnicity	0.77	1	0.64	.43	0.36	2.82*
Age	30.98	22.6	35.46	13.72	-12.86	-3.25**
family size	5.81	6.6	5.39	3.82	1.21	0.99
Male	3.63	5.07	2.86	2.23	2.21	3.49***
Female	3.12	2.87	3.25	1.18	-0.38	-1.02
Experience in goat farming	4.56	3	5.39	4.22	-2.39	-1.82
Land Area	0.71	1.52	0.27	.77	1.25	8.21***
Access to credit	0.63	1.06	0.39	.63	0.67	3.77***
Number of out migrants	0.28	0.4	0.21	.45	0.19	1.29
Training taken	0.63	1	0.43	.49	0.57	4.37***
Separate shed	0.74	0.6	0.82	.49	-0.22	-1.42
Awareness	0.74	1	0.61	.44	0.39	3.04*
Goat number	19.53	37.80	9.7500	37.83	28.05	2.451
No of boar goat	13.18	37.80	0	38.49	37.80	3.443

Source: Field survey, 2015

Note: ***, ** and * indicate significant at 1Percent, 5 percent and 10 percent levels.

Compound growth rate of goat population and meat production over the years

Compound growth rate of goat population and meat production over the years have been compared through regression analysis and found population growth of goat has been increased by 36% whereas the meat production has been increased by only 35%.

Observations 15

R square 0.992998835

Adjusted R square 0.992460284

Table 2: Regression results for growth rate of population of goat over the years

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistic	p-Value
Constant	15.62572988	0.007598	2056.482	3.21E-37
Goat population	0.035884846	0.000836	42.93989	2.15E-15

Table: 3 Regression results for growth rate of goat meat production over the time periods

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistic	p-Value
Constant	10.47	0.008	1326.621	9.58E-35
Goat meat production	0.035	0.001	40.36	4.77E-15

Observation: 15

R square: 0.992084074

Adjusted R square: 0.991475156

F-statistics: 1629.258834

Comparisons of goat for performance and economic age identification

Farmers have perceived that optimum age for meat production for both khari and Boer is 18 months but weight gained by Boer goat was 45kg whereas the weights gain of Khari goat ranges from 26 to 28kg. PPR and coccidiosis were the major diseases of Khari goat in the selected district.

Table 4: Comparison of goat for performance and economic age identification

S,N.	Categories	Boer (N=15)	Khari (N= 30)
1	Optimum age for meat production	In an average 35kg meat in 6 month	In an average 15month to 2 years for 35 kg meat
2	Effect due to seasonal change	Low effect due to seasonal change	High effect due to seasonal change (Disease occurrence)
3	Average meat increment i)Farmers view ii)Research Station iii)Research Station	100 gram/day (100%) 65.50 gram/day (100%) 91.22gram/day (50% cross)	60 to 70 gram/day 83.1gram/day
4	Available fat	High incomaparision to khari goat	Low incomparision to boer goat

(Note: The data was collected on 2015/16 when the ample feed was not available to feed the Boer goat due to blockade problem)

Scenario of weight gain of Boer and Khari kids

Figure 1 shows the growth rate of 25% Boer goat cross with Khari goat. Equation depicted that with 1 unit increase in month there is 2.73 unit increment in the Boer meat production.

Figure 1. Growth rate of 25% Boer cross with Khari goat

Figure 2 shows the growth rate of 100% Khari goat. Equation depicted that with 1 unit increase in month there is 1.730 unit increment in the meat production of khari goat.

In comparison between two different breeds Boer and Khari goat Boer goat seem to be more profitable in terms of meat product by a given time.

Constraints and potentiality of scale up:

Almost 100% farmers involved in Boer goat are raising this breed of goat on their own risk. They buy/import goat, raise on their own knowledge and are creating market by themselves. Furthermore, they are crossing Boer breed with other breed of goat. Within the interviewed farmers, 75% of them reported that only the cross of khari a local breed of goat with 100% pure Boer breed can show prominent characteristics of Boer that red headed, large framed, white body with smooth hair, cylindrical and straightway backward curved horn in second and third generations too. As well the consumers are only willing to pay more money for specific colour of Boer. That is why monopoly in the breed development, dissemination and marketing, fixing price by the private sector basically through commercial farmers were observed. Beside this, less information about the insurance scheme to both improved goat production. Insufficient knowledge about improved shed construction as well as management of improved breeds was also observed.

Basically, Boer goat rearing site of Dhading was prioritized for the private - private partnership. Whereas, private goat farm was established as source centre for Boer goat and seems to have monopoly in marketing. Due to unaffordable price to small and marginal farmers, insignificant number of Boer goat has been disseminated. Therefore,

there is less chance for small holder farmers to adopt Boer goat production in existing condition.

Opportunities

More than 50% of the total respondents who are not currently raising Boer goats are eager to raise them unless the price of goat will be reasonable that is NRs.500/kg for live weight. Meanwhile, farmers have their own niche that is farmers of Bihar and UP. Almost 100% kids (6 month) are exported to India. The exported price range vary from NRs. 2500 to 4000 for 100% Boer cross. Therefore, huge gap in demand and supply was observed. There is an increasing demand for goat meat while at the same time short supply is met from import suggesting significant scope of scaling up.

- Increasing price trend of goat meat.
- Creation of jobs locally at production and post-production levels.
- Emerging opportunities on value addition.
- Inadequate live animal market system.

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